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Impact Of Monetary And Non-Monetary Rewards On Teachers' Productivity In Public Secondary Schools In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated reward management strategies and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State. A correlational research design was adopted, guided by three research questions and corresponding hypotheses. The study population consisted of 7,254 teachers (3,642 males and 3,612 females) in 286 public senior secondary schools across the 23 local government areas of Rivers State. The sample size comprised 725 teachers selected from 29 schools, determined through a multistage sampling technique. Twenty-nine schools were chosen using simple random sampling through balloting, while the teachers were selected using a proportionate stratified random sampling technique. The names of the schools were folded on pieces of paper and drawn randomly to ensure equal chances of selection. Two researcher-designed instruments, the Reward Management Strategies Questionnaire (RMSQ) and Teachers' Productivity Questionnaire (TPQ), were employed for data collection. These instruments were structured with four-point response options: Very High Extent (4), High Extent (3), Low Extent (2), and Very Low Extent (1). The instruments underwent face validity to assess their adequacy, wording, appropriateness, and suitability for the study. This was achieved by presenting them to three experts: two from the Department of Educational Management and one from Measurement and Evaluation at the University of Port Harcourt. The reliability coefficients for the TPQ and RMSQ were computed as 0.86 and 0.85, respectively, using Cronbach's Alpha. The process of administration and data collection lasted two weeks. Out of 725 copies of the instruments distributed, the researcher and assistants successfully retrieved 689 copies, representing a 95% return rate. The hypotheses were tested using a t-test associated with simple regression, while the extent of the relationship was determined using the coefficient of determination (R^2), multiplied by 100%. The findings indicated that monetary rewards are significantly related to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State, to a very high extent. The study further revealed that compensation rewards significantly relate to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State, to a very high extent. Based on these findings, it was concluded that reward management strategies significantly enhance teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State. The study recommended, among other things, that school principals should utilise internally generated revenue to provide monetary rewards for teachers who excel in their job responsibilities.

Keywords: Monetary Rewards, Non-Monetary Rewards, Teachers' Productivity, Public Secondary Schools, Rivers State

INTRODUCTION

The success of any educational system depends on the dedication and effectiveness of its teachers. In public secondary schools, where challenges are prevalent and resources are often limited, motivating and rewarding teachers becomes even more critical. Human resources are the major assets of any organisation, as they work toward achieving organisational goals while striving to meet their individual needs and aspirations (Obasi & Asodike, 2014). Teachers play an essential role in schools, serving as the driving force that propels the institution forward. Without teachers, other resources within the school risk becoming unproductive and underutilised. The productivity of teachers is vital for schools to achieve their educational goals and objectives. Teachers' productivity refers to their ability to perform assigned duties effectively, a factor significantly influenced by the rewards provided. It is also defined as the ability to meet goals while making efficient use of the limited resources available.

Armstrong (2010) argued that one of the most important, if not the most critical, responsibilities of school managers is to ensure that teachers achieve high levels of productivity. This argument highlights the fact that the success of any school organisation is a reflection of the performance of its teachers. The better the teachers perform, the better the school performs, and vice versa. Therefore, the government needs to implement appropriate reward mechanisms to motivate teachers toward higher productivity. Financial rewards, such as increased pay, bonuses, remuneration, etc., and non-financial rewards, such as recognition, promotion, increased responsibilities, and opportunities for personal growth, are among the reward management strategies that encourage teachers to be more productive in their service delivery.

Reward management strategies are designed to motivate teachers by satisfying their esteem needs and aligning their efforts with the school's goals. The success of any organisation is inherently tied to the effectiveness of its human capital. Reward management is described as developing, implementing, maintaining, communicating, and evaluating reward processes (Murlis as cited in Galanou et al., 2010). The objectives of reward management include achieving corporate, individual, and union goals and objectives through the formulation and implementation of appropriate policies and strategies for the organisation. Recent evidence highlights that teacher quality is crucial for student achievement, yet it appears to be unrelated to most observable teacher characteristics. Rewarding teachers for high performance and attracting a pool of high-performing teachers are promising policies for improving student outcomes. The ongoing quest to improve public education has prompted policymakers and researchers to focus on strategies for increasing teachers' productivity.

In organisations with effective performance measures, employees are motivated by improved pay, terms, and conditions of service, which result in higher productivity and better-quality outputs. The motivation for this report is twofold. Firstly, while substantial research has been conducted on the economic effects of incentive schemes, there is limited understanding of the patterns of performance-related pay both within and across countries.

To achieve the desired level of productivity, certain conditions must be met by school management. Firstly, there must be a conducive work environment to support teachers' effectiveness. Secondly, rewards are essential to enhancing teachers' performance.

Rewards are defined as all forms of financial and tangible benefits provided by employers to employees in exchange for their efforts (Milkovich & Newman, 1999). These rewards can take the form of direct or indirect payments. Direct payments may include cash payments issued on a weekly or monthly basis, while indirect rewards may consist of financial or non-financial benefits offered to employees as a result of their continued tenure with the organization, such as fringe benefits or supplementary pay (Dessler, 2011; Jean, Ngui & Robert, 2017). Teachers play a critical role in fostering the development of skills and abilities in students, who are the future leaders of tomorrow.

Statement of the Problem

Research and personal experience have shown that most of the teachers record low productivity in secondary schools in Rivers State. The underperformance of the teachers can be seen in their inability to properly prepare lesson notes, come to class on time, record classroom control and management, cover

instructional content, as well as give objective assessment and feedback as expected. These issues from the teachers may have led the students to always record low achievement in internal and external examinations. More so, most of them have turned out to practice truancy, absenteeism and off-task behaviours. This ugly trend in teachers' productivity, which has led to students' poor academic performance, may be a result of poor reward management strategies. In many public secondary schools in Rivers State, teachers are being asked to take on more responsibilities without a corresponding reward. The work and living environments for many teachers seem to be poorly structured, leading to lower self-esteem and demotivation. Teachers resort to individual help projects. Most secondary school teachers engage in petty trading in their various schools, most especially teachers in the rural areas. Some other teachers demand money for scores from parents, as high grades and scores are reserved for the highest bidders. Thus, most teachers spend little time helping students to learn. This ugly trend has led to most institutions being compromised, leading to disruptions of academic programmes at all levels of Nigerian education. Teachers declare industrial actions for improved funding, better working conditions and upgrading of teaching and learning facilities. These disruptions affect the school calendar and often lead to school closures for weeks and even months. Most times, students are denied the opportunity to make up for lost time. This may result in low student academic accomplishments and poor teachers' productivity. Teachers' seriousness in teaching depends on their motivation and professional competencies. Teachers will give their very best when they have a feeling or trust that their efforts will be rewarded by the management. Despite all, more often than not, there is low productivity and a low level of performance. School principals are left wondering how to acquire, let alone, retain highly productive teachers; hence affecting the targets set by the school management in one way or another, which are not met due to a declining level of performance and lack of knowledge on how rewards affect productivity. If these challenges are left unabated, the secondary school standard in Rivers State will continue to fall, and the schools will lose highly productive teachers. This study, therefore, examined the relationship between reward management strategies and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to investigate reward management strategies and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives were to:

1. Examine the extent of relationship between monetary reward and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. Assess the extent of relationship between compensation reward and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. Find out the extent of relationship between welfare reward package and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

This study answered the following research questions;

1. What is the extent of relationship between monetary reward and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. What is the extent of relationship between compensation reward and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State?
3. What is the extent of relationship between welfare reward package and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study;

1. There is no significant relationship between monetary reward and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between compensation reward and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

3. There is no significant relationship between welfare reward package and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study are of great significance to educational managers responsible for overseeing public secondary schools. These managers include the Ministry of Education, the Secondary Schools Board, School Administrators, Teachers, and other Researchers.

i. Ministry of Education: This study will serve as a valuable guide in planning comprehensive reward management strategies for secondary schools.

ii. Secondary Schools Board: The findings will provide critical insights into effective reward management strategies that can enhance teachers' productivity.

iii. School Administrators: The study will offer practical guidance on reward strategies aimed at improving teachers' productivity and fostering positive outcomes.

iv. Teachers: These findings will help teachers understand how different reward strategies implemented by school managers affect their productivity and performance.

v. Researchers: The study will serve as a reference point for both current and future researchers conducting similar studies. It will also provide a foundation for future scholars seeking to refine teacher reward strategies and address knowledge gaps in this area.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study adopted a correlational research design, which investigated the extent of the relationship between the variables: reward management strategies and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State, without the researcher controlling or manipulating any of them. The population for this study comprised 7,254 (3,642 males and 3,612 females) teachers in 286 public senior secondary schools in the 23 local government areas of Rivers State. The sample size for the study consisted of 725 teachers selected from 29 schools. A multistage sampling technique was employed to determine the sample size. Twenty-nine (29) schools were selected using a simple random sampling technique through balloting, while teachers were chosen using a proportionate stratified random sampling technique. The names of the schools were folded on pieces of paper and picked randomly to ensure equal opportunities for selection. Two researcher-designed instruments, Reward Management Strategies Questionnaire (RMSQ) and Teachers' Productivity Questionnaire (TPQ), were used for data collection. The instruments were structured on four-point response options of Very High Extent (4), High Extent (3), Low Extent (2) and Very Low Extent (1) respectively. The instruments were subjected to face validity to determine their adequacy, proper wordings, appropriateness and suitability for the study. This was done by giving the instruments to three experts, from the Department of Educational Management and one from Measurement and Evaluation at the University of Port Harcourt. The experts were requested to critique, add or remove items that were not relevant to the study and assess the importance and clarity of the items in addressing the research questions based on the purpose of the study, research questions and hypotheses. Their corrections were strictly applied to the final production of the instrument. Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the reliability coefficient of the instruments. The two sets of instruments were administered to 30 teachers who were not part of the sample of the study. The two instruments were administered to the teachers once. The Cronbach alpha was used because the instruments were not dichotomously scored, and it also enabled the researcher to determine the internal consistency of the instruments. The reliability coefficient of TPQ was computed to be 0.86, while that of RMSQ was 0.85, respectively. The instruments were administered and retrieved personally by the researcher with the help of three research assistants. A total of 725 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents. The three research assistants were given a briefing on the mode of administration of the instruments to the respondents. The administration of the instruments was carried out on a direct and face-to-face method of data administration and collection. The process of administration and collection of the instruments lasted for two weeks. Out of the 725 copies of the instruments distributed, the researcher and the assistants were

able to retrieve 689 copies, representing a 95% return rate. The hypotheses were tested with a t-test associated with simple regression, while the extent of the relationship was determined using the coefficient of determination (R²) multiplied by 100%. This gave the decision rule of Very Low Extent (0-25), Low Extent (26-50%), High Extent (51-75%) and Very High Extent (76-100%) respectively.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the extent of relationship between monetary reward and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Simple Regression of the Extent of Relationship between Monetary Reward and Teachers' Productivity

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Decision
1	.977 ^a	.954	.954	Very High Extent

Data in Table 1 revealed that the regression and regression square coefficients are 0.977 and 0.954, respectively. The predictive power is determined by the coefficient of determinism. The coefficient of determinism of 95.4% reveals that monetary reward relates to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent.

Research Question 2: *What is the extent of relationship between compensation reward and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Simple Regression of the Extent of Relationship between Compensation Reward and Teachers' Productivity

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Decision
1	.985 ^a	.971	.971	Very High Extent

Data in Table 2 revealed that the regression and regression square coefficients are 0.985 and 0.971, respectively. The predictive power is determined by the coefficient of determinism. The coefficient of determinism of 97.1% reveals that compensation reward relates to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent.

Research Question 3: *What is the extent of relationship between welfare reward package and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 3: Simple Regression of the Extent of Relationship between Welfare Reward Package and Teachers' Productivity

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Decision
1	.989 ^a	.978	.978	Very High Extent

Data in Table 3 revealed that the regression and regression square coefficients are 0.989 and 0.978, respectively. The predictive power is determined by the coefficient of determinism. The coefficient of determinism of 98.9% reveals that welfare reward relates to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between monetary reward and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: t-test Associated with Simple Regression of the Extent of Relationship between Monetary Reward and Teachers' Productivity

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.598	.273		5.846	.000
	Monetary	.956	.008	.977	119.117	.000

Data in Table 4.7 reveals that the t-test value of 119.117 associated with simple regression is rejected because the significance value of 0.00 is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, monetary reward significantly relates to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between compensation reward and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 5: t-test Associated with Simple Regression of the Extent of Relationship between Compensation Reward and Teachers' Productivity

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.006	.219		4.592	.000
	Compensation	.973	.006	.985	151.373	.000

Data in Table 5 reveals that the t-test value of 151.373 associated with simple regression is rejected because the significance value of 0.00 is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, compensation reward significantly relates to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between welfare reward package and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 6: t-test Associated with Simple Regression of the Extent of Relationship between Welfare Reward Package and Teachers' Productivity

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.795	.193		4.126	.000
	Welfare	.979	.006	.989	173.169	.000

Data in Table 6 reveals that the t-test value of 173.169 associated with simple regression is rejected because the significance value of 0.00 is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, welfare reward significantly relates to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings revealed that monetary rewards significantly relate to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent. This aligns with Moses (2016), whose study on the effect of reward systems on the performance of teachers in secondary schools in Kasama District found that monetary incentives enhance performance-based activities. Similarly, Oyira, Regina, Nkamare, Lukpata, Uwa, and Mbum (2015) agreed that monetary rewards have a positive impact on employees' performance.

The hypothesis further confirmed that monetary rewards significantly relate to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent. This finding is supported by Nalweyiso (2012), who also observed a positive relationship between monetary rewards and staff commitment at the College of Education. Likewise, Mehta (2014) found that monetary rewards significantly influence employee performance and job satisfaction. Additionally, Met and Juhary (2015) affirmed that monetary motivation has a direct effect on employees' job performance. These findings suggest that monetary rewards are crucial for motivating teachers to excel in their teaching responsibilities. Providing monetary incentives and rewards to high-performing teachers can increase their drive and commitment toward achieving educational goals in secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

The study also revealed that compensation rewards significantly relate to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent. This finding corresponds with Hameed et al (2014), who noted the positive impact of compensation on employee performance. In agreement, Ngwa, Adeleke, Agbaeze, Ghasi, and Imhanrenialena (2019) associated compensation with staff performance. Onyango (2014) further reported that employee compensation contributes to organisational performance. The hypothesis reaffirmed that compensation rewards significantly relate to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent. This indicates that increased compensation leads to enhanced staff performance. Overall, the study concluded that compensation has a positive connection with teachers' performance in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Additionally, the study found that welfare rewards significantly relate to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent. This finding corresponds with Siwale, Hapompwe, Kukano, and Silavwe (2020), who discovered a link between reward systems and employee job performance. Muchiri (2016) similarly found that salaries, wages, paid vacations, paid leave, travel allowances, and bonuses predict task performance in organisations. Consistent with these findings, Okwudili (2015) identified good incentive packages as determinants of job performance. The hypothesis confirmed that welfare rewards significantly relate to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent. This implies that welfare packages, such as salaries, paid vacations, paid leave, travel allowances, and bonuses, enhance satisfaction and subsequently improve performance. These components of extrinsic rewards are essential for boosting teachers' productivity in their teaching responsibilities.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that reward management strategies significantly contribute to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, monetary rewards, compensation rewards and welfare rewards were identified as factors that determine teachers' productivity to a very high extent. This implies that the more teachers are rewarded, the greater their teaching productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are made:

1. The school principals should provide monetary rewards through the internally generated revenue to teachers who are productive in areas of their job schedule.
2. Teachers who use their resources for effective instructional delivery should be adequately compensated to enhance their productivity.
3. The teachers in public secondary schools in Rivers State should constitute a functional welfare committee with some defined reward modalities that can encourage financial welfare provision to teachers who are in need.

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